

Supplementary material: Inferring clusters of orthologous and paralogous transcripts

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S1-Text : Difference between the approach of our method and that of Guillaudeau et al. [1]

Our algorithm is based on the identification of putative isoorthologous transcripts taking into account both structural similarity (i.e in terms of the composition in exons) and evolutionary context, given a multiple sequence alignment of gene and transcript sequences. The approach of Guillaudeau et al. aims to identify structurally conserved transcripts without considering the evolutionary relationships between them. The method of Guillaudeau et al. starts by identifying conserved functional sites (donor and acceptor splice sites, start and stop codons) and exon blocks among three orthologous genes. Given the orthology relationships between functional sites, orthologous transcripts are then defined as transcripts sharing a conserved splicing structure.

S2-Text : Decomposition of multiple sequence alignment (MSA) into blocks.

Figure 1 shows that, despite its simplicity, the decomposition of MSA into blocks yields small numbers of blocks even for very long MSA.

Figure 1: Relationship between the length of the multiple sequence alignment, and the number of blocks resulting from the decomposition of the alignment.

References

- [1] Nicolas Guillaudeau, Catherine Belleannée, and Samuel Blanquart. Identifying genes with conserved splicing structure and orthologous isoforms in human, mouse and dog. *BMC genomics*, 23(1):1–14, 2022.